

[4+2]Cycloaddition Reactions and other Reactions of 2-(Sulphinylamino)thiazole

G. A. AHMED

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Zagazig University, Zagazig, Egypt

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2-(Sulphinylamino)thiazole (1) on reaction with some dienes under Diels-Alder condition gave the [4+2]cycloaddition products (2a,b). Compound 1 also underwent reaction with nitrile oxide to form 3*H*-1,2,3,5-oxathiadiazole-2-oxide (3). The reactivity of 1 towards active methylene compounds was studied. Some Schiff bases (5a-c) were obtained by the reaction of 1 with aromatic aldehydes. Further, the reaction of 1 with copper and sodium metals produced azo and thiazo products 6 and 7 respectively.

Wichterle and Rocek¹ reported the first example of a Diels-Alder cycloaddition of *N*-sulphinyl dienophile with a 1,3-diene. The same workers also investigated a few simple transformations of these interesting heterocyclic adducts. During the past 30 years relatively little additional works have been reported in this area other than a number of observations that various *N*-sulphinyl compounds bearing electron-withdrawing groups undergo the cycloaddition at temperature generally well below those usually required for all carbon Diels-Alder reactions². Interestingly, *N*-sulphinyl compounds derived from alkylamines are reported to be inactive as dienophile

Results and Discussion

The known *N*-sulphinylamine compounds derived from aromatic amines were obtained by the reaction of aromatic amine with thionyl chloride^{3,4}. Following this procedure we prepared the 2-(sulphinylamino)thiazole (1) by heating 2-aminothiazole with thionyl chloride (Scheme 1). Compound 1 was heated with 1,3-dienes, namely, butadiene and 2,3-dimethylbutadiene to give the corresponding cycloaddition products (2a,b)⁵

Nitrile oxides react exothermally with *N*-sulphinyl compounds to form 3*H*-1,2,3,5-oxathiadiazole-2-oxides, in some cases quantitatively.^{6,7} So, compound 1 was reacted with *p*-chlorobenzhydroxamylchloride in presence of anhydrous triethylamine to give 4-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-3-(2-thionyl)-1,2,3,5-oxathiadiazole-2-oxide (3). Treatment of 1 with active methylene compounds, namely, ethyl cyanoacetate and ethyl chloroac-

etate gave the addition products 4a,b.

When *N*-sulphinylamino compounds are heated with

aldehydes having no α -H atoms, SO_2 is eliminated and sulphinylimines are formed in good yields⁸. Compound 1 was reacted with aromatic aldehydes, namely, benzaldehyde, 4-chloro- and 4-nitrobenzaldehyde in the presence of HCl to give the known Schiff bases (5a-c)⁹.

The syntheses of symmetrical azo compounds and also thioazo compounds from *N*-sulphonylamines are described¹⁰. So a mixture of compound 1 and finely divided copper when heated yielded the azo compound (6). Compound 1 when heated with sodium metal gave the sulphodiimide derivative (7).

Experimental

M.p.s. are not corrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were measured on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) at 60 MHz on a Varian EM-360-L spectrometer.

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

2-(Sulphonylamino)thiazole (1): A mixture of 2-aminothiazole (0.01 mol) and thionylchloride (0.01 mol) in dry ether (20 ml) was refluxed for 10 h. Ether was then evaporated and the solid produced was crystallised from benzene, (57%), m. p. 85–86°; ν_{max} 1 080 cm^{-1} (NSO); δ 7.5–7.7 (2H, m, ArH).

Formation of 2a,b: A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and the diene (10 ml), namely, butadiene or 2,3-dimethylbutadiene was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then evaporated and the solid was dried and crystallised from toluene: 2a (63%), m.p. 158–59°; b (71%), 142–43°; ν_{max} 1 100–1 120 (S=O), 1 625–1 650 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ 2.2 (6H, s, 2×CH₃), 2.6 (2H, s, CH₂), 3.5 (2H, s, CH₂SO), 7.4–7.6 (2H, m, ArH).

4-(p-Chlorophenyl)-3-(2-thionyl)-1,2,3,5-oxathiazol 2-oxide (3): Anhydrous triethylamine (5.1 g) was added rapidly with vigorous stirring to an ice-cooled solution of 4-chlorobenzhydroxamylchloride (9.5 g) in anhydrous ether (250 ml). After a few minutes, the triethylammoniumchloride was filtered off and washed with a little anhydrous ether, and 2-(sulphonylamino)thiazole (1; 10.9 g) was added to the combined filtrate. The mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 2 h, then filtered, the filtrate was evaporated, and

the residue was crystallised from benzene, (68%), m. p. 71–72°; ν_{max} 1 630–1 640 (C=N), 1 150 cm^{-1} (SO), δ 6.5–8.0 (6H, m, ArH).

Formation of 4a,b: A mixture 1 (0.01 mol) and active methylene compounds, namely, ethyl cyanoacetate and ethyl chloroacetate (0.01 mol) in presence of a few drops of triethylamine and benzene (15 ml) was heated for 3 h. The solid obtained after cooling was crystallised from benzene: 4a (71%), m.p. 118–19°. ν_{max} 1 140–1 160 (S=O), 1 625–1 650 (C=N), 1 730–1 740 (C=O), 3 300–3 330 cm^{-1} (NH); 4b (74%), 132–34°; additional ir band at 2 230 cm^{-1} (C=N).

Schiff bases (5a,b): A slow current of dry HCl gas was passed through solution of aromatic aldehydes (0.1 mol) namely, benzaldehyde, 4-chloro-, 4-nitrobenzaldehyde and 2-(sulphonylamino)thiazole (1; 0.1 mol) in benzene (50 ml), and the solution was refluxed in the HCl stream for 3 h. Benzene was then evaporated and the residue crystallised from benzene: 5a (48%), m. p. 127–28°, b (59%), 170°; c (53%), 139°; ν_{max} 1 620–1 640 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ 7.3–8.2 (m, ArH and N=CH).

Azobithiazolyl (6): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and finely divided copper (0.01 mol) in dry xylene (50 ml) was refluxed for 15 h and then filtered off. The filtrate was left to cool. The solid produced was crystallised from benzene, (42%), m.p. 176°; ν_{max} 1 575–1 650 cm^{-1} (N=N, C=N); δ 7.0–7.5 (4H, m, ArH).

Azothobithiazolyl (7): In dry xylene (10 ml), a mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and finely divided sodium metal (0.01 mol) (prepared by heating sodium metal in xylene) was refluxed for 10 h. The reaction mixture was then filtered and the filtrate was allowed to cool. The solid produced was crystallised from toluene as pale yellow solid (65%), m.p. 198–99°; δ 6.8–7.5 (4H, m, ArH).

References

- O. WICHTERLE and J. ROCEK, *Chem. Listy*, 1953, **47**, 1768.
- S. M. WEINREB and R. R. STAIB, *Tetrahedron*, 1982, **38**, 3087.
- P. HOPE and L. A. WILES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 5386.
- G. KRESZE, A. HORN, R. PHILIPPSON and H. TREDE, *Chem. Ber.*, 1965, **98**, 3401.

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5. R. HUISGEN, W. MACK and E. ANNESER, *Angew Chem.*, 1961, **73**, 656.
6. P. RAJAGOPALAN and H. U. DAENIKER, *Angew. Chem.*, 1963, **75**, 91.
7. F. ELOY and R. LENAERS, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1965, **74**, 129.
8. R. ALBRECHT, G. KERSZE and B. MLAKAR, *Chem. Ber.*, 1964, **97**, 483.
9. M. R. MAHMOUD, A. M. EL-NADY and M. M. A. HAMED, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 596.
10. T. H. EVEDEJS, D. L. EBERLEIN and VARIE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **49**, 573.

